

Electrode kinetics and ternary complex formation of [Cd^{II}-antibiotics-vitamin-B₁] system vis-a-vis kinetics of electrode reaction

Farid Khan* and Firoj Khan

Electrochemical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University,
Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com; farid.fk@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Polarographic technique was used to study the ternary complex formation of Cd^{II} with neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxy-tetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V and penicillin-G as primary ligands and vitamin-B₁ as a secondary ligand at pH = 7.30 ± 0.01 and μ = 1.0 M KNO₃ at 298 K. The nature of current voltage curves was reversible and diffusion controlled. Cd^{II} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes with these drugs as confirmed by Schaap and McMaster method. The sequence of stability constants of complexes was neomycin < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < penicillin-V < penicillin-G that can be explained on the basis of nature of ligands and steric hindrance between metal and ligands.

Keywords : Electrode kinetics, ternary complexes, cadmium(II) systems.

Antibiotics are natural compounds produced by plant microorganisms. Now a days, most of the diseases are controlled by these antibiotics¹. Vitamin-B₁ is also an important drug given simultaneously with other drugs in serious diseases². On the other hand, Cd is the most toxic element in the environment to which industrial civilization has exposed itself. The content of Cd is fixed in human blood and serum. When the concentration of Cd is increased, the human beings suffer from several serious diseases like cancer of the bladder, intestine, leukemic system, prostate and rectum. The content of Cd in blood and serum can be reduced by ligands therapy. At present, 2,3 dimerceptopropan-1-ol, nitrilotriacetic acid and H₄EDTA and its derivatives have been used for Cd toxicity. They initially reduce the toxicity of Cd but eventually increase the nephrotoxicity. Therefore, the use of these drugs against Cd toxicity is questionable³. Till now, there is no suitable antidote available for Cd toxicity⁴. Therefore the study of Cd^{II} complexes with selected antibiotics and vitamin-B₁ has great importance. The present paper deals with the ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with selected antibiotics and vitamin-B₁ for which no reference is available in the literature.

Results and discussion

Cd^{II} gave two electron reversible reduction and diffusion controlled wave at pH = 7.30 ± 0.01 and μ = 1.0

M KNO₃ at 298 K⁵. The nature of current-voltage curves for complexes is also reversible. The concentrations of Cd^{II}, KNO₃, and gelatin (as suppressor) in the test solution were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for de-aeration before recording the current-voltage curves.

The concentration of antibiotics varied from 0.5 mM to 30.0 mM at two fixed concentration of vitamin-B₁ i.e. 0.025 M and 0.050 M. The $E_{1/2}$ values became more negative with the addition of vitamin-B₁ to the [Cd-antibiotics] system which showed ternary complex formation. Schaap and McMaster method⁶ confirmed the formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. The data and plots of F_{ij} [X, Y] against [X] (where F_{ij} is Schaap and McMaster function to evaluate the stability constant β_{ij} ⁶, X = antibiotics, Y = vitamin-B₁ and i and j are their stoichiometric numbers) for [Cd-neomycin-vitamin-B₁] system were given in Table 1 and Fig. 1 respectively. The Fig. 1 is used to determine the values of functions F_{00} , F_{10} , F_{20} and F_{30} to calculate the stability constants. The values of F_{00} [X, Y] can be calculated by putting the values of $(E_{1/2})_m$, $(E_{1/2})_c$, I_m and I_c in the following equation

$$F_{00}[X, Y] = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{0.435nF}{RT} \left\{ (E_{1/2})_m - (E_{1/2})_c \right\} + \log \frac{I_m}{I_c} \right]$$

(where symbols have the usual meanings⁶). In this way the values of $F_{00}[X, Y]$ for various concentrations of $[X] = [\text{antibiotics}]$ can be obtained. By plotting $F_{00}[X, Y]$ against $[X]$, the value of constant A can be determined.

The values of $F_{10}[X, Y]$, $F_{20}[X, Y]$, $F_{30}[X, Y]$ ---- can be calculated as follows :

$$F_{10}[X, Y] = (F_{00}[X, Y] - A)/[X]$$

$$F_{20}[X, Y] = (F_{10}[X, Y] - B)/[X]$$

$$F_{N0}[X, Y] = (F_{N-1}[X, Y] - \text{constant})/[X].$$

This process is continued till the plot between $F_{N0}[X, Y]$ against $[X]$ is a straight line which confirmed that the complex formation is over. Thereafter the values of stability constants can be calculated as follows :

$$F_{00}[X, Y] = \{\beta_{00} + \beta_{01}[X] + \beta_{02}[Y]^2 + \beta_{03}[Y]^3\}[X]^0 + \{\beta_{10} + \beta_{11}[Y] + \beta_{12}[Y]^2\}[X] + \{\beta_{20} + \beta_{21}[Y]\}[X]^2 + \{\beta_{30}\}[X]^3$$

$$\text{or } F_{00}[X, Y] = A + B[X] + C[X]^2 + D[X]^3$$

To know the values of β_{11} and β_{12} , the study has been carried out at two constant concentrations of secondary ligand $[Y] = [\text{Vitamin-B}_1]$. The values of stability constants of complexes were given in Table 2.

To compare the stability of binary and ternary complexes, the values of mixing constant $\log K$ was calculated by the following equation⁶

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

Fig. 1. Plot of $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ vs $[X]$ for $[\text{Cd-neomycin-vitamin-B}_1]$ system : (\blacklozenge) $F_{00}[X, Y]$, (\blacksquare) $F_{10}[X, Y] \times 10^2$, (\blacktriangle) $F_{20}[X, Y] \times 10^5$, (\blackcross) $F_{30}[X, Y] \times 10^8$.

The values of $\log K_m$ were -0.525 , -0.975 , -0.935 and -0.0765 for $[\text{Cd-neomycin-vitamin-B}_1]$, $[\text{Cd-chlortetracycline-vitamin-B}_1]$, $[\text{Cd-tetracycline-vitamin-B}_1]$ and $[\text{Cd-}$

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ values of $[\text{Cd-antibiotics-vitamin-B}_1]$ system

$[\text{Cd}^{II}] = 0.050 \text{ M}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M KNO}_3$, $\text{pH} = 7.30 \pm 0.01$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

[Vitamin-B ₁] = 0.025 M							(Vitamin-B ₁) = 0.050 M					
[Neo.] $\times 10^3$	$\log I_m/I_c$	$E_{1/2} - V$ vs SCE	$F_{00}[X, Y]$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^2$	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^5$	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^9$	$\log I_m/I_c$	$E_{1/2} - V$ vs SCE	$F_{00}[X, Y]$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^2$	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^5$	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ $\times 10^9$
0.00	-	0.586	-	-	-	-	-	0.586	-	-	-	-
0.50	0.0683	0.611	7.22	20.34	16.14	15.84	0.0683	0.621	15.54	32.69	31.20	15.84
1.00	0.0137	0.613	9.05	28.49	16.22	15.84	0.0137	0.623	18.75	48.38	31.28	15.84
2.00	0.0137	0.620	15.21	45.03	16.37	15.83	0.0208	0.628	29.90	73.98	31.44	15.85
3.00	0.0208	0.626	24.77	61.88	16.53	15.82	0.0280	0.634	47.48	111.89	31.60	15.80
4.00	0.0208	0.631	37.82	79.05	16.69	15.80	0.0284	0.639	71.56	144.13	31.75	15.82
5.00	0.0280	0.636	54.48	96.54	16.85	15.84	0.0353	0.644	102.36	176.68	34.91	15.83
6.00	0.0353	0.640	74.88	114.35	17.01	15.84	0.0427	0.648	139.63	207.54	32.02	15.80
8.00	0.0427	0.646	126.93	150.90	17.32	15.83	0.0427	0.654	234.91	276.24	32.39	15.84
10.00	0.0427	0.652	196.95	188.74	17.64	15.84	0.0503	0.659	358.11	344.20	32.71	15.84
20.00	0.0503	0.670	799.83	396.81	19.22	15.82	0.0503	0.677	1419.82	702.95	34.29	15.83
30.00	0.0503	0.681	1916.37	636.72	20.81	15.84	0.0579	0.688	3294.03	1093.38	35.87	15.83

$\log A = 0.79$, $\log B = 3.08$, $\log C = 6.20$, $\log D = 7.20$

$\log A = 1.14$, $\log B = 3.23$, $\log C = 6.49$, $\log D = 7.20$.

Table 2. Stability constants of [Cd-antibiotics-vitamin-B₁] system[Cd^{II}] = 0.5 mM, $\mu = 1.0 M$ KNO₃, pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01, Temp. = 25°C

Primary ligand	log β_{01}	log β_{02}	log β_{10}	log β_{20}	log β_{30}	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
Neomycin	-	-	3.00	5.00	7.20	3.60	5.31	7.78
Chlortetracycline	-	-	3.50	7.10	8.00	4.20	7.61	8.20
Oxytetracycline	-	-	4.13	7.51	-	-	7.83	8.36
Tetracycline	-	-	4.24	7.82	9.12	4.60	8.25	9.45
Penicillin-V	-	-	4.38	-	9.20	4.75	8.38	9.60
Penicillin-G	-	-	4.53	8.08	9.80	4.90	8.61	10.00
Vitamin-B ₁	2.16 (2.20) ^a	3.25 (3.30) ^a	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aA. K. Jain and F. Khan, *J. Elect. Chem. Soc. India*, 1996, 45, 115; data at pH = 8.50.

penicillin-G-vitamin-B₁] respectively. The negative values of log K_m showed that binary complexes are more stable than their ternary complexes. The complexes of compositions 1 : 1 : 1 in case of [Cd-oxytetracycline-vitamin-B₁] and [Cd-penicilline-V] are not formed and the values of log K_m are not calculated. It is clear from the values of stability constants of complexes that neomycin formed the complexes of lowest stability⁷. In case of tetracyclines; all the tetracyclines have the same structures except in the difference in R₁ and R₂ positions. The less stability of chlortetracycline complex than that of oxytetracycline complex is due to the presence of more electron withdrawing Cl at R₁ in the former in place of H in the latter. In case of tetracycline, H is present both at R₁ and R₂ hence, there is least electronic disturbances in tetracycline in comparison to other tetracycline complexes⁸. This order of stability constant supported the order of the pK values of the ligands⁹. In case of both penicillin-V and penicillin-G, it is the ring nitrogen and O of the carboxylic group which take part in complex-

ation with Cd^{II}. The greater stability of penicillin-G complexes than that of penicillin-V complexes is also supported by the order of the ligands pK values¹⁰. The structures of the ligands and their complexes are given in Fig. 2. In case of vitamin-B₁, it is the N of pyrimidine ring, which can take part in bond formation with Cd^{II}.

It is clear from the values of stability constants³ of the complexes that vitamin-B₁ and antibiotics used either singly or simultaneously might be effective to reduce the toxicity of Cd *in vivo*.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Cd^{II}, the antibiotics and vitamin-B₁ were taken in the ratios of 1 : 40 : 40 and current voltage curves were obtained in different pH values. It has been observed that the maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was obtained within the pH range 7.10–8.50, but pH 7.30 was selected for studying the complexes in human blood pH. An Elico digital pH meter (Model-LI-120) was used to keep the pH of the analyte at 7.30 \pm 0.01 adjusted by using dilute solutions of HNO₃ or NaOH as required. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer was added to stabilize the pH of the analyte. 0.001% gelatin was used as the maximum suppressor. The current voltage curves were obtained on a manual polarograph using polyflex galvanometer (PL-50). The polarographic cell was of Latinin and Lingane⁵ type in which polarographic capillary of 5.0 cm in length with 0.04 mm in diameter was used. The $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ value was 2.40 mg^{2/3} s^{-1/2} at 60.02 cm effective height of mercury. As the resistance of the cell was less than 300 Ω , IR correction was not made.

Fig. 2. [Cd-Chlortetracycline-vitamin-B₁] system.

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(The structure of the other systems are available on request).